

Comparisons and Contrasts between Traditional Religion and Christianity

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Abstract: This short article consists of a comparative analysis that attempts to uncover the relationship between Christianity and traditional African religion. It examines how these two religions conceptualize God, the spirit world, sin and salvation, intercession with God or with the spirit world, as well as witchcraft and healing. While the two religions appeared to be completely different, it was found that there are elements in Christianity and traditional African religion, which brought together and compared are of common character, a comparison that leads to mutual enrichment and transformation in the two religions.

Key words: Christianity and African Traditional Religion, The Spirit World, Sin and Salvation, Superstition and Witchcraft, Sacrifice and Worship.

1. Introduction

The African Traditional Religion, which is still in place today, can be compared to Christianity through their similarities and differences. Even though their differences outnumber their similarities (Adamo, 2011), I like to look at the similarities in a bigger sense. For example, they have traditions, healing, sacrifice, and worship, but they hold a great deal of differences involved with them.

African Traditional Religion and Christianity, both being religions, need to be spread throughout the people who follow it, which includes different rules and standards to the religion. However, they enforce a different way of spreading the religion. As Idang (2015) puts it, African Traditional Religion works on oral traditions, as the clan elders follow the same rules that their ancestors did many years ago. In a traditional context, the traditions, rites or customs practiced are not necessarily written down anywhere. On the contrary, Christianity depends a lot on the biblical [sacred] scriptures according to which Christians follow the rules, laws and traditions taught or practiced by the early church fathers, and these cannot be changed simply by word of mouth (Jambrek & Jambrek, 2010).

The use of oral communication in traditional religion causes an unanswered question as to whether their traditions can be changed through the years or not. However, some of their traditions have not kept up with today's science and discoveries, which proves how they are true to their oral traditions. For example, the creation myths like the reason the rabbit did not get the long tail is because he was the last one to show up for the tail meeting. These stories seem funny to us today, but it is also important to notice, even though most would say this is not correct, the true belief these people hold in their religion that has not been changed by today's discoveries. Same stories can be found in Christianity. For example, Christians believe Jonah was swallowed by a big fish but God provided him with protection and a way to survive in the fish, even though unbelievers would laugh at this statement.

2. Healing

Healing in the African Traditional Religion and Christianity is a way to show belief that the healer has spiritual powers to cure something that seems physically impossible. One thing to note is that an African traditionalist is at peace when he has a proper relationship with God, spirits and other people, so a broken relationship leads to disaster, including disease (Nahashon, 2009). In this sense, healing means bringing together what is separate, giving center to what is divided, overcoming the division between God and mankind, man and the world, man and himself (Boikanyo, 2020). The African Traditional

Religion uses Izangoma (witchdoctors) and Izinyanga to heal the people with the spirit ancestors and plants for medicine (Mokgobi, 2014). The witchdoctors, more evil, are called through a dream or vision, to determine the misfortune of someone by communicating with ancestors. The Herbalist, or Izinyanga, uses things such as hippo fat and plants to make umuthi, or medicine. These medicines are used for people who are dealing with a variety of things, such as physical illness, love, misfortune, or lightning.

Christian healing includes the use of perseverance in prayer and intercessions to God that the person who is dealing with physical or mental illness will have God's healing hand on them and fix whatever is wrong. This can take one day to many years, but the people do not have to give anything in return, like African Traditional Religion, to whoever is praying for them. Most Christians have the resources to go to a regular doctor for pharmaceutical medicine.

3. Sacrifice

Although there are different sacrifices and offerings in the Old Testament, such as sin and guilt offerings, which were aimed at obtaining cleansing after one has respectively sinned unintentionally or deprived another of his rights / profaned something holy (Dockery, et al., 1992), Christians believe that these prefigured Christ, an eternal sacrifice for the sin of man. Sacrifice in Christianity means sacrificing your life, such as Martyrdom, on earth to Jesus to be promised eternal life in heaven (Frankiel, 2000). Baptism, a ritual cleansing of the soul, is used as a personal sacrifice to give everything to Jesus, the Lord and Savior.

Sacrifice in African Traditional Religion means sacrificing an animal to pay an Izangoma or to celebrate a special occasion. For example, if people of the African Traditional Religion hold a funeral, they will sacrifice an animal, like a goat, to represent the status of the departed from the shadow to ancestor. They will then eat the meat and use the blood for rituals after the animal has bellowed and ancestors have proven and accepted the sacrifice (Mvunabandi, 2008). Sacrifice is also used, in the traditional African context, when there is a problem in the family and the family gives sacrifices and offerings to God to influence God to save them from the bad situation they are going through.

4. Worship

The other very big difference between African Traditional Religion and Christianity is the worship. In African Traditional Religion, they do believe in a genderless god with the three names: Umvelingqangi, uNkulunkulu, and uThixo (Badoian, 2014). However, to them, the entire universe is filled with spirit such as trees, rocks, and rivers. The people that they truly worship are their ancestors. Each person has his/her own ancestors which he/she believes can zap him/her with lightning at any time. The ancestors reside in the spiritual world, Kwelimumoya. The ancestors' roles include giving guidance, judging and punishing, protection, and control. According to Mangany & Buitendag (2013), ancestors are the major factor to African Traditional Religion because the people know that the ancestors are constantly overlooking them. Christians feel this control and protection from God; however, they feel that God will never do anything to personally harm the person. God, to Christians, is a fatherly figure that cares for you at your weakest and guides you in His plan for your own life. Christians do know that God judges them and knows that they sin; however, without punishing He asks that you plead for forgiveness, only to be completely filled with the Holy Spirit.

Ubuntu, is a way to show others care, compassion through a positive and reflective morality. For example, people will adopt their neighbor's child if the parents have abandoned it or passed away. All of the adults in the community are parents, brothers or sisters and are open to sharing and caring throughout. An example of openness would be the weddings and funerals being open to anyone and everyone. They believe celebration of anything is a good way to get everyone together. In the Christian context, grace is translated as an unmerited gift. Through Adam's sin, man's relationship with God was broken, the thing considered to be born into a new kingdom of Satan due to man's alienation from the Kingdom of Light (Zwaan, 2014). That means that the human race has been subject to Satan's power and slavery until God supplied His undeserved gift of divine favor in the salvation of sinners, and of divine influence working in man for his regeneration and sanctification (Britannica, 2020). Therefore, all men are subject to the sin and wrath of God, just as all are open to the saving grace of God.

Ubuntu, in modern society can be fulfilled if everyone has the right heart and mind. I personally think that it is a great thing to be a help to anyone around me, because as a Christian, that is what I am called to do. However, I am not sure, in America, if Ubuntu could survive due to the many distractions in American lives. People miss funerals because of business meetings, and cannot make it to weddings because they are too stressed from work. I honestly wish that my community could try to take on some of these habits of Ubuntu way of life, because you never know when a neighbor needs compassion and care from someone but is too scared to walk next door because he/she has never personally talked with you.

5. Sin and salvation

In a Christian sense, sin has severed the relationship between a man and God and this relationship can only be restored through faith in Jesus Christ, the God-given Savior. Jesus is the only acceptable and eternal sacrifice for sin, freeing a man from the bondage of sin and Satan. Being said that for a Christian salvation reflects a God's saving grace from sin, in African religion, the reality of human salvation is closely related to the experience of life.

A traditionalist considers salvation to come from God, but describes it as a movement from distress towards safety, victory and submission of your enemies under your rule or a sign of defeat against whatever causes unhappiness in the life of a person (Boikanyo, 2020); , in fact a concept of human empowerment. For them, salvation is defined in terms of evil spirits, daily hardships, and a lack of good relationship with ancestral spirits, rather than from sin, as Christians believe.

6. The concept of God and of spirit world

As Christians believe in One God, African traditionalists also believe in God but with some differences in the concept.

Christians believe in Trinity as a loving and eternal unity of three divine persons: the Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit¹, the one who created the universe ex nihilo² and created humankind to enjoy, glorify God and manage the other creation³.

African traditionalists on their end believe in a god, different from a human, but use different images to help them conceptualize God as they confess to know little to nothing about him (Sophia, 2009). God is experienced as an omnipresent reality, but with less sovereign power, because the African is held captive by subordinate beings, the spirits that play the major role in man's efforts (Sophia, 2009).

While Christians also believe in existence of sprits, they make a clear distinction between Holy Spirit and evil spirits that Jesus has overcome. Jesus Himself not only cast out demons but also told his followers how to overcome evil spirits (Matthew 17:14-20; Luke 4:31-44); the Apostle Paul mentions the gift of discerning of spirits in 1 Cor. 12:10. The reality is that Christians do not neglect the spirit world. This is what Paul wrote and Christians should know: *"... our wrestling is not against flesh and blood, but against the principalities, against the powers, against the world-rulers of this darkness, against the spiritual hosts of wickedness in the heavenly places"* (Ephesians 6:12). Unlike Christians, African traditionalists feel surrounded by spirits, primary ancestral spirits, whom they believe can be appeased and controlled through different rituals and sacrifices, so that they cannot have any effect on the living generation (Conteh, 2008). For them, when a family member dies, he is reincarnated into a new life form and this ancestral spirit remains as long as the living can remember. The living may call on the support of the Ancestral Spirits in their plans, and may attribute all misfortune to their failure to appease the Ancestral Spirits. While Christians also call for the support of the Holy Spirit, the whole idea is the third person of the Trinity rather than the ancestral spirits, who play more active roles than God does for a traditionalist.

¹ John 1:1; Matthew 28:19; Deuteronomy 6:4 and John 14:26

² Gen 1-2; Heb 11:3; Ex 20:11

³ Gen 1:26-28; Isaiah 43:7; Psalm 8; Psalm 37:4 ; Rev 1: 26:28; Ephesian 2:10

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